

EFFECT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM ON STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT AND INTEREST IN PHYSICS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OGBIA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BAYELSA STATE.

BY

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of flipped classroom on students' interest and achievement in physics among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Three research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised 1564 Senior Secondary School II (SS II) Physics students. The sample size of 326 SS II students from two schools were drawn using simple random sampling. The instrument for data collection was Electromagnetism Achievement Test (EAT) which was developed by the researcher and validated by three experts from the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Kuder- Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of .80 was obtained. Adjusted Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study showed that Physics students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom had significant mean achieve score when compared to those taught using lecture method. In line with the findings, the researcher recommended among others that Physics teachers should adopt the flipped classroom approach in teaching electromagnetism to enhance students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom, Lecture Method, Academic Achievement, Electromagnetism

Introduction

Physics is a branch of science that deals with the study of matter, energy, space, and time. It seeks to understand the fundamental principles that govern the universe and the interactions between different components of the physical world. Physics plays a crucial role in various aspects of one's lives, particularly in the field of medicine where it contributes to advancements such as X-rays, radioisotopes, and nuclear magnetic resonance imaging (Ankeli et al., 2020). Additionally, the progress and discoveries in physics underpin the development of technologies like lasers, electron microscopes, synchrotron radiation, and electronics.

Physics stands as the fundamental science among the physical sciences. According to Ankeli et al. (2020), Physics plays a crucial role in our understanding of the natural world and has led to technological advancements that have transformed society. Physics as a subject has remained one of the most relevant science subjects that those in medicine, pharmacy, astronomy, space science, Information Communication Technology (ICT) and engineering and other aspects of science majorly depend on (Aina& Akintunde, 2014). Physics serves as the foundational framework for understanding the intricate interplay of forces and phenomena in the natural world, and within

this vast discipline, electromagnetism stands out as a crucial branch that investigates the relationship between electric and magnetic fields.

Electromagnetism is a branch of physics that studies the interrelation between electric and magnetic fields, encompassing the behaviour of charged particles, electromagnetic waves, and the fundamental forces that govern their interactions. It is described by a set of equations known as Maxwell's equations and plays a pivotal role in various technological applications, ranging from electric power generation and transmission to the functioning of electronic devices (Aina& Akintunde, 2014). According to Maxwell (2014), electromagnetism has wide-ranging applications in various fields, including electrical engineering, telecommunications, and technology. Understanding these fundamental principles is crucial for the development of technologies such as electric power generation, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and many other electromagnetic devices.

Despite the vital importance of physics in getting the students ready for an increasingly advanced scientific world, their performance has consistently failed to meet the expected benchmarks. Students' low enrolment and poor achievement in physics has been recorded over the years. The West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Chief examiners' reports (2018-2021) in physics when compared with other science subjects, indicated low enrolment and poor performance of students generally despite the favourable standards of the question paper

and the moderate severity of the marking scheme. Researchers such as Olorukooba (2017) and Gambari (2020), identified causes of students' poor achievement in physics to include inappropriate instructional strategies, discrimination among students due to ethno-religious crises, abstract nature of physics concepts, lack of qualified teachers, poor infrastructure and inadequate laboratory facilities, non-availability and non-utilization of physics instructional materials. The application of innovative teaching methods in physics not only enhances students' understanding of fundamental principles but also fosters a dynamic and engaging learning environment that encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The academic achievement of students in physics is influenced by a complex interplay of various factors, including teaching methods.

Teaching methods refer to the strategies, approaches, and techniques that educators use to facilitate learning and help students acquire knowledge, skills, and understanding. While teaching methods encompass a broad range of instructional approaches, the lecture method which is most widely used specifically involves the delivery of information through spoken discourse, making it one of the traditional and most commonly used forms of classroom instruction (Eze, 2016). The lecture method is a traditional instructional approach in which a teacher or instructor verbally presents information to a large group of students. During a lecture, the instructor typically speaks while students listen and take notes, with limited opportunities for active participation.

A flipped classroom is a teaching model where students review instructional materials, such as video lectures and readings, before class, allowing in-class time to focus on active learning and problem-solving. This approach shifts the traditional lecture-based method, giving students control over initial content exposure at their own pace outside the classroom (Abeysekera & Dawson, 2015). In-class activities emphasize discussions, collaborative projects, and hands-on tasks that reinforce concepts, promoting deeper understanding (Bishop & Verleger, 2013). Research suggests that flipped classrooms improve student engagement, critical thinking, and performance compared to conventional methods (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). Teachers in flipped settings act as facilitators, guiding students through complex topics and offering personalized support during class time (Chen et al. 2014). The effectiveness of this model has been noted in various disciplines, including STEM and business education, highlighting its adaptability and positive outcomes (Lo & Hew, 2017). The flipped classroom approach has been linked to improved academic achievement, as it allows students to engage with instructional content at their own pace before class, leading to better preparation. Studies have shown that students in flipped classrooms often demonstrate higher test scores and better retention of concepts compared to those in traditional lecture-based settings (Bishop & Verleger, 2013). This is because class time is used for interactive activities, problem-solving, and teacher-guided support, which helps to reinforce

understanding and clarify difficult topics (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). As a result, the flipped classroom creates an environment that promotes active learning, which is a key factor in enhancing students' academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

Physics is a core science subject in secondary schools, yet students in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, consistently record low achievement and interest in the subject. Traditional teacher-centered instructional methods dominate classrooms, leading to passive learning, poor conceptual understanding, and declining student performance in physics. Reports from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) revealed persistent mass failure in physics in Bayelsa State, raising concerns among educators and parents (WAEC Chief Examiner's Report, 2023). Students often perceive physics as abstract and difficult, resulting in a lack of interest and reduced enrollment in science-related careers. Research suggests that innovative teaching approaches, like the flipped classroom model, can enhance students' engagement and academic achievement in science subjects.

However, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach in improving physics achievement and interest among secondary school students in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State. Teachers in the area have limited exposure to student-centered and technology-driven teaching methods, further contributing to the learning challenges.

Without adopting new instructional strategies, students may continue to struggle, leading to poor performance in external examinations and reduced interest in physics. There is, therefore, a need to investigate the effect of the flipped classroom approach on students' achievement and interest in physics in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of flipped classroom on students' achievement and interest in Physics among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study investigated to:

1. determine the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS II students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.
2. ascertain the mean interest scores and standard deviations of SS II students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.
3. the mean achievement, interest scores and standard deviations of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean interest scores and standard deviations of SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those

taught using the lecture method in both pre-test and post-test?

2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those taught using the lecture method in both pre-test and post-test?
3. What are the mean interest scores, and standard deviations of male and female SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach?
4. What are the mean achievement and standard deviations of male and female SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

Research Method

Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. Nworgu (2015) described a quasi-experimental research design as one where it's not feasible to randomly allocate participants to both experimental and control groups. The population for the study comprised 1564 Senior Secondary School II (SS II) Physics students. The sample size of 326 SS II students from two schools was drawn using simple random sampling technique. It comprised 165 SS II students from two intact classes in one school making the experimental group (89 males and 76 females) and 161 SS II students from two intact classes in the other school making the control group. The instruments for data collection were Electromagnetism Interest Scale (EIS) and Electromagnetism Achievement Test (EAT) which was developed by the researcher and validated by three experts from the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The final form of Electromagnetism Interest Scale (EIS) and Electromagnetism Achievement Test (EAT) had seven (7) items and fifty (50) items respectively. Cronbach Alpha Coefficient formula and Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula were used to estimate the reliability of EIS and EAT and a reliability index of .80 and .78 were obtained respectively.

The mode of test administration for this study involved a pre-test and post-test approach to

assess students' achievement and interest in physics. The pre-interest and pre-test were administered before the intervention to establish baseline knowledge and interest levels, while the post-interest and post-test were administered after the flipped classroom strategy was implemented. Both tests were covering key physics concepts, and were supervised by trained research assistants to ensure consistency and reliability of the data collected. Concurrently, conventional Physics teachers were trained on implementing the flipped classroom to teach students in the experimental group. A lesson plan centered around electromagnetism was devised. Conversely, teachers in the control group were not provided formal training, continuing to teach using their lecture method. This treatment lasted for six (6) weeks, and it also aligned with the standard school schedule. The timetable allocated one (1) double period (80 minutes) and one (1) single period (40 minutes) for Physics every week. These periods were used to teach the students for four (4) weeks, where each topic lasted for one (1) week. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The choice for the use of ANCOVA is because intact classes were used and initial differences cannot be guaranteed. The null hypothesis was rejected if probability value is less than or equal to the significant value of .05 ($P \leq 0.05$) and if otherwise ($P > .05$), it was not rejected.

Results

The results are presented based on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What are the mean interest scores and standard deviations of SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those taught using the lecture method?

Table 1: Adjusted mean interest scores and standard deviations of students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those taught using the lecture method in both pre-test and post-test

Instructional Strategies	N	Adjusted Mean	Interest Scores
		\bar{X}	SD
Flipped Classroom	165	12.40	3.20
Lecture	161	11.00	3.48

Results in Table 1 shows that the adjusted mean interest scores of students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and lecture methods are 12.40 and 11.00 respectively. This result indicates that students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach had the higher mean interest score than those taught using lecture method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those taught using the lecture method in both pre-test and post-test?

Table 2: Adjusted mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and those taught using the lecture method in both pre-test and post-test

Instructional Strategies	N	Adjusted Mean	Achievement Scores
		\bar{X}	SD
Flipped Classroom	165	34.53	6.26
Lecture	161	32.34	8.37

Results in Table 2 shows that the adjusted mean achievement scores of students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach and lecture methods are 34.53 and 32.34 respectively. This result indicates that students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach had the higher mean achievement score than those taught using lecture method.

Research Question 3

What are the mean interest scores and standard deviations of male and female SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach?

Table 3: Adjusted mean interest scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach

Gender	N	Adjusted Mean	Interest Scores
		\bar{X}	SD
Female	75	13.13	3.35
Male	90	12.63	3.08

Results in Table 3 shows that the mean interest scores of female and male students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach are 13.13 and 12.63 respectively. This result indicates that female students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach had a higher mean score when compared to their male counterparts.

Research Question 4

What are the mean achievement and standard deviations of male and female SS II Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach?

Table 4: Adjusted mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach

Gender	N	Adjusted Mean	Interest Scores
		\bar{X}	SD
Female	75	34.88	6.43
Male	90	34.74	6.14

Results in Table 4 shows that the mean achievement scores of female and male students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach are 34.88 and 34.74 respectively. This result indicates that female students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach had a higher mean score when compared to their male counterparts.

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the mean interest scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	1009.41	1	1009.41	111.97	.00
Main Effects	Strategies	144.14	1	144.14	15.99	.00
Residual		2911.77	323	9.02		
Total		4065.32	325	12.51		

In Table 5, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of the main effects (strategies) is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P <$

.05, there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	5103.83	1	5103.83	129.43	.00
Main Effects	Strategies	389.46	1	389.46	9.88	.00
Residual		12737.32	323	39.43		
Total		18230.61	325	56.09		

In Table 6, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of the main effects (strategies) is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at P < .05, there is significant difference between the mean achievement scores of SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom and those taught using lecture method.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance on the mean interest scores of SS II male and female students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	460.93	1	460.93	61.24	.00
Main Effects	Strategies	3.42	1	3.42	0.45	.50
Residual		1219.44	162	7.53		
Total		1683.79	164	10.27		

In Table 7, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .50 of the main effects (gender) is greater than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that at P <.05, there is no

significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

H0₄: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism with flipped classroom

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	1451.13	1	1451.13	47.32	.00
Main Effects	Gender	0.80	1	0.80	0.03	.87
Residual		4967.86	162	30.67		
Total		6419.79	164	39.15		

In Table 8, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .87 of the main effects (gender) is greater than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that at $P < .05$, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female SS II students taught electromagnetism using flipped classroom.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study showed that Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom method outperformed those taught with the traditional lecture method. The performance was a significant one. The findings may have been from the increased access to pre-recorded video lectures and interactive class activities in the flipped classroom. It aligns with the work of Bishop and Verleger (2013), who found that the flipped classroom approach improves students' understanding and academic performance in science subjects by allowing more interactive and engaging learning experiences. Similarly, Zainuddin and Halili (2016) reported that students in flipped learning environments achieved better learning outcomes compared to those in conventional lecture settings, emphasizing the effectiveness of this innovative teaching method.

The findings of the study revealed that Physics students who were taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach demonstrated a higher level of interest compared to those instructed through the traditional lecture method. This suggests that the interactive nature of flipped learning, which allows students to engage with instructional materials before class and participate in hands-on activities during lessons, enhances their enthusiasm for the subject. This aligns with the work of Bishop and Verleger (2013), who found that the flipped classroom model fosters greater student engagement and motivation in science subjects by shifting the focus from passive listening to active learning. Similarly, Awidi and Paynter (2019) reported that students in flipped learning environments showed increased interest and active participation, particularly in complex topics like electromagnetism, due to the opportunity for self-paced learning and classroom discussions. The study also highlights that the flexibility of the flipped classroom method enables students to revisit instructional materials at their own pace, which contributes to sustained interest and deeper understanding. These findings reinforce the need for innovative teaching methods in physics education to improve students' engagement and overall learning experience.

The findings of the study also revealed that the interest and achievement of Physics male and female students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom approach were not significant. This may have demonstrated the equal level of involvement of both male and female students in the flipped classroom approach. The findings is in line with the work of Bishop and Verleger (2013), who found that the flipped classroom approach improves students' understanding and academic performance in science subjects by allowing more interactive and engaging learning experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Schools should integrate the flipped classroom method into Physics instruction, especially for complex topics like electromagnetism, to enhance students' academic performance and understanding.
2. Teachers should undergo professional development programmes to equip them with the skills needed to effectively implement the flipped classroom approach and maximize student interest and engagement.
3. Educational institutions should invest in the creation and distribution of quality video tutorials and online materials to support flipped classroom teaching, ensuring students can access learning content outside traditional class hours.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that Physics students taught electromagnetism using the flipped classroom method achieved better academic performance compared to those taught through the traditional lecture method. It was also observed that students exposed to the flipped classroom approach demonstrated a higher level of interest in learning electromagnetism than their counterparts in the lecture method group. These results suggest that the flipped classroom strategy enhances both students' performance and interest in Physics concepts. Therefore, educators should consider adopting the flipped classroom model to improve teaching and learning outcomes in Physics.

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